

GLOBAL VAN-CONG EFFECTIVE KINETIC, GRAVITATIONAL POTENTIAL, AND TOTAL ENERGIES, OBTAINED IN THE GEOSTATIONNARY SATELLITE (GS) – EARTH INTERACTION SYSTEM, AND ENHANCED BY OUR EMPIRICAL GLOBAL EFFECTIVE KINETIC MASS OF THIS GS, EXPRESSED AS A FUNCTION OF ANY SPEED (OR ANY RELATIVITY) (40)

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ABSTRACT

In this work, we present the new expressions of global effective kinetic, gravitational potential and total energies, obtained in the Geostationary Satellite (GS)-Earth interaction system, as those given in Equations (4, 5, 6), and enhanced by a new global effective kinetic mass of the GS, as that given in Eq. (1). Some concluding remarks are given as follows. At the low speed $v \ll c$, c being the light speed, given in the non-relativistic case, they are found to be correct. At $v=c$, given in the relativistic case, the kinetic energy is found to be equal to: $m \times c^2 \times \left[\frac{2+p}{4} \right]$, for $p > 0$, and, in particular, for $p=2$, to: $m \times c^2$, in good accordance with that proposed by Einstein in 1905 [1], m being the rest mass of the GS, as those shown in Table 1.

KEYWORDS: Global effective kinetic-potential-total energies, global effective kinetic mass, light speed, relativity, non-relativity.

First of all, from the expression of the kinetic energy of Geostationary Satellite (GS), with its rest mass $m(= 5060 \text{ Kg})$, in motion with a speed v , being equal to the light speed $c= 2.9979 \times 10^8 \left(\frac{m}{s}\right)$, $\frac{2m \times c^2}{2}$, given by Einstein in 1905 [1-3], we now propose its **gobal effective kinetic mass**, valid at any v , by [4] :

$$m^*(v; p > 0) = m \times \left(1 + p \times \frac{v^2}{c^2}\right), \quad (1)$$

being increased with increasing v , and noting that at lowest v : $m^*(v; p) \simeq m$, given in the non-relativistic case, and then, at $v=c$, given in the relativistic case: $m^*(v = c; p) = m \times (1 + p)$.

Then, from Eq. (1), this GS is in motion, due to the **global effective Newton force**:

$$F_{\text{GEN}}^*(v; p) \equiv m^*(v; p) \times \frac{dv}{dt} = m \times \left(1 + p \times \frac{v^2}{c^2}\right) \times \frac{dv}{dt}, \quad (2)$$

where $\frac{dv}{dt}$ is its acceleration. Further, it is attracted by the Earth of the mass $M = 5.97219 \times 10^{24} \text{ kg}$, due to the **global effective gravitational force**, defined by:

$$F_{\text{GEG}}^*(v; p) \equiv -\frac{GMm^*(v;p)}{r^2} = -\frac{GMm \times \left(1 + p \times \frac{v^2}{c^2}\right)}{r^2}, \quad (3)$$

where r is the distace between the GS and the Earth, and $G = 6.6743 \times 10^{-11} \frac{m^3}{kg \times s^2}$ is the universal gravitational constant.

From Eq. (2), noting that $\frac{dv}{dt} \times dr = v dv$, our **global effective kinetic energy** is defined by:

$$K^*(v; p) \equiv \int F_{\text{GEN}}^*(v; p) \times dr = \int m \times \left(1 + p \times \frac{v^2}{c^2}\right) \times v dv = m \times v^2 \times \left[\frac{2 + p \times \frac{v^2}{c^2}}{4}\right]. \quad (4)$$

Eq. (4) is reduced to the correct result at the lowest v ($\ll c$) as: $\frac{m \times v^2}{2}$, given in the non-relativistic case, and at $v=c$, given in the relativistic case, to: $K_o(p) \equiv m \times c^2 \times \left[\frac{2+p}{4}\right]$, which gives rise to a following assumption, by putting: $x = \frac{2+p}{4}$.

If x is known, then p is determined by : $p=4x-2$.

For example, (i) if $x=3/4$, then $p=1$, accoding to : $K_o(p = 1) = \left(\frac{3}{4}\right) \times mc^2$, (ii) if $x=1$, then $p=2$, accoding to : $K_o(p = 2) = mc^2$, in good accordance with that proposed by Einstein in

the relativistic case [1], (iii) if $x=5/4$, then $p=3$, according to : $K_o(p = 3) = (\frac{5}{4}) \times mc^2$, and so on. This assumption is used to determine $K_o(p)$, given in next Table 1 in Appendix 1.

Further, from Eq. (3), our global effective gravitational energy, $U^*(v, r; p)$, is defined by:

$$U^*(v, r; p) \equiv - \int_{\infty}^r F_{GEG}^*(v; p) \times dx \equiv - \int_{\infty}^r - \frac{GMm^*(v;p)}{x^2} dx = - \frac{GMm^*(v;p)}{r} = - \frac{GMm \times (1+p \times \frac{v^2}{c^2})}{r},$$

being reduced to the correct result at the lowest $v (\ll c)$ as: $= - \frac{GMm}{r}$, given in the non-relativistic case, and at $v=c$, to: $- \frac{GMm \times (1+p)}{r}$, given in the relativistic case.

Here, we choose: $r = r_{GS} = 35786 \times 10^3 \text{ m}$, being the distance from the GS to the Earth at **Perihelion** (or at **Aphelion**), and $v_{GS} \leq v \leq c$, $v_{GS} = 3.1 \times 10^3 (\frac{m}{s})$, being the GS speed at

Perihelion (or at **Aphelion**). That gives : $U^*(v; p) = - \frac{GMm \times (1+p \times \frac{v^2}{c^2})}{r_{GS}}$, (5)

according at $v=c$ to: $U_o(p) \equiv - \frac{GMm \times (1+p)}{r_{GS}}$, given in the relativistic case.

Therefore, from Equations (4, 5), the **global effective total energy**, $E^*(v; p)$, is found to be given by:

$$E^*(v; p) \equiv m \times v^2 \times \left[\frac{2+p \times \frac{v^2}{c^2}}{4} \right] - \frac{GMm \times (1+p \times \frac{v^2}{c^2})}{r_{GS}}, \quad (6)$$

according at $v=c$ to: $E_o(p) = K_o(p) + U_o(p) = m \times v^2 \times \left[\frac{2+p}{4} \right] - \frac{GMm \times (1+p)}{r_{GS}}$.

Furthermore, it is interesting to evaluate the relative errors between $K^*(v; p)$ and $E^*(v; p)$, defined by:

$$RE(v; p) \equiv 1 - \frac{E^*(v;p)}{K^*(v;p)}. \quad (7)$$

Then, in following Table 1 in Appendix 1, the numerical results of $RE(v; p)$, $K^*(v; p)/K_o(p)$, $U^*(v; p)/U_o(p)$ and $E^*(v; p)/E_o(p)$ are obtained for $p=1, 2$ and 3 , respectively, using Equations (7, 4, 5, 6), noting that, for a given p , $RE(v; p)$ decreases with increasing v , and at $v=c$ one obtains $K^*(v; p) \cong E^*(v; p)$, with a precision of the order of 3.966×10^{-10} .

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APPENDIX 1

Table 1. In the **Geostationary Satellite-Earth interaction system**, in which the values of m , r_{GS} and v_{GS} are given in above Table 1, the numerical results of $RE(v; p)$, $K^*(v; p)/K_o(p)$, $U^*(v; p)/U_o(p)$ and $E^*(v; p)/E_o(p)$, are obtained by using Equations (7, 4, 5, 6), respectively, noting that $v_{GS} \leq v \leq c$.

$X(v)=v/c$	$RE(v; p)$	$K^*(v; p)/K_o(p)$	$U^*(v; p)/U_o(p)$	$E^*(v; p)/E_o(p)$
Here, for $p=1$ and at $v=c$, $K_o(p) = \left(\frac{3}{4}\right) \times mc^2 = 3.410719974 \times 10^{20}$ J, $U_o(p) = -1.12721483 \times 10^{11}$ J and $E_o(p) = 3.4107199725 \times 10^{20}$ J, suggesting that $E_o(p) \cong K_o(p)$, with a precision of the order of $3.30491745 \times 10^{-10}$.				
1.03406×10^{-5}	2.31810334	$7.12849487 \times 10^{-11}$	0.50	$-9.3960929 \times 10^{-11}$
0.09	$3.07245230 \times 10^{-8}$	0.00542187	0.50405	0.00542187
0.30	$2.87269553 \times 10^{-9}$	0.0627	0.545	0.0627
0.40	$1.66393421 \times 10^{-9}$	0.1152	0.58	0.1152
0.60	$7.93553667 \times 10^{-10}$	0.2832	0.68	0.2832
0.80	$4.81184759 \times 10^{-10}$	0.5632	0.82	0.5632
0.90	$3.94220434 \times 10^{-10}$	0.7587	0.905	0.7587
0.95	$3.60045327 \times 10^{-10}$	0.87316875	0.95125	0.87316875
1	$3.30491745 \times 10^{-10}$	1	1	1

Here, for $p=2$ and at $v=c$, $K_o(p) = mc^2 = 4.54762663100 \times 10^{20}$ J, in good agreement with that, proposed by **Einstein in 1905**, $U_o(p) = -1.69082225 \times 10^{11}$ J and $E_o(p) = 4.5476266298 \times 10^{20}$ J, suggesting that $E_o(p) \cong K_o(p)$, with a precision of the order of $3.71803255 \times 10^{-10}$.

1.03406×10^{-5}	2.31810334	$5.34637115 \times 10^{-11}$	0.33333333	$-7.04706968 \times 10^{-11}$
0.09	$3.08469656 \times 10^{-8}$	0.00408281	0.33873333	0.00408280
0.30	$2.98150049 \times 10^{-9}$	0.04905	0.39333333	0.04905
0.40	$1.76286019 \times 10^{-9}$	0.0928	0.44	0.0928
0.60	$8.70781003 \times 10^{-10}$	0.2448	0.57333333	0.2448
0.80	$5.38434630 \times 10^{-10}$	0.5248	0.76	0.5248
0.90	$4.42954895 \times 10^{-10}$	0.73305	0.87333333	0.73305
0.95	$4.04932754 \times 10^{-10}$	0.85850312	0.935	0.85850312
1	$3.71803255 \times 10^{-10}$	1	1	1

Here, for $p=3$ and further at $v=c$, $K_o(p) = \frac{5}{4} \times mc^2 = 5.6845332890 \times 10^{20}$ J, $U_o(p) = -2.25442966 \times 10^{11}$ J and $E_o(p) = 5.6845332871 \times 10^{20}$ J, suggesting that $E_o(p) \cong K_o(p)$, with a precision of the order of $3.96590094 \times 10^{-10}$.

1.03406×10^{-5}	2.31810334	$4.27709692 \times 10^{-11}$	0.25	$-5.63765575 \times 10^{-11}$
0.09	$3.09684285 \times 10^{-8}$	0.00327937	0.256075	0.00327937
0.30	$3.08167780 \times 10^{-9}$	0.04086	0.3175	0.04086

0.40	$1.84902149 \times 10^{-9}$	0.07936	0.37	0.07936
0.60	$9.29955113 \times 10^{-10}$	0.22176	0.52	0.22176
0.80	$5.76990566 \times 10^{-10}$	0.50176	0.73	0.50176
0.90	$4.73867945 \times 10^{-10}$	0.71766	0.8575	0.71766
0.95	$4.32609060 \times 10^{-10}$	0.84970375	0.926875	0.84970375
1	$3.96590094 \times 10^{-10}$	1	1	1
